

Research Trends of Affective Commitment among Teacher: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract:- Affective commitment among teachers is an important aspect in determining the success of education reform and school effectiveness. Teachers who have a high affective commitment will give maximum effort and all their abilities to achieve the school's vision and goals. Affective commitment research has grown rapidly in recent years. Several studies with various background issues related to the complexity and dynamics of affective commitment have been investigated. Therefore, this study aims to determine current trends in affective commitment and then to find the research opportunity for further research. This study uses a bibliometric analysis approach based on the Scopus database. Various methods have been used, such as frequency analysis, VOS viewer for data visualization, citation and metric analysis. Based on the title, abstract, and keywords, this study succeeded in obtaining 4.266 articles related to affective commitment. Based on the mapping results obtained 297 articles of affective commitment in education and 83 articles of teacher affective commitment. Based on this one finding, it can be guaranteed that commitment among teachers is still widely studied by other researchers. Thus, research related to affective commitment, especially to teachers, can be an opportunity for further research related to current trends

Keywords:- *Affective commitment, teacher, bibliometric analysis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are a determinant of educational success. The role of teachers in education has been recognized by many parties, both academics, practitioners, and researchers. In an educational institution, teacher-focused research is one of the important things, to understand some of the factors that influence teachers to stay in an educational institution and become effective classroom teachers [17]. apart from their duties as educators, teachers are part of an organization with various characteristics. Empirically, teachers and the performance they produce have been studied previously [8] and there are several factors that affect a teacher's performance, one of these factors is teacher commitment [2]. Commitment is one of the important factors to ensure the development and success of an organization [18]. Organizational commitment is needed to show employee loyalty and responsibility in the organization. This encourages someone to try to achieve the success of organizational goals and be loyal to continue to be a member in an organization. So, when teachers already have a commitment to their organization, they will try to devote and do their best to achieve the school's vision and goals [9]. Meyer and Allen explain that there are 3 dimensions in organizational

commitment, namely affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment. Schultc said that affective commitment is the emotional attachment of members to the organization caused by feelings of self and members of the organization towards organizational goals which are carried out through hard work that increases involvement and feelings of pleasure and enjoyment in the organization. Affective commitment is also called commitment as attitude, which is a condition when individuals consider the extent to which their values and goals are in accordance with the values and goals of the organization [19]. Individuals with this commitment will identify themselves with the values and goals of the organization and want to maintain their membership [19][13], so that effective commitment works as a driver of various competencies that can improve the performance of a member of the organization. Rhoades also said that affective commitment is also one of the factors that determine the loyalty and dedication of a member to his organization. An organization member who has affective commitment tends to show a sense of belonging to the organization, is able to increase his involvement in various organizational activities, a desire to remain in the organization and participate in trying hard to achieve organizational goals [1]. Therefore, affective commitment is a person's strong desire to continue working in the organization, which is caused because members of the organization have a relationship with the principles, values, and goals of the organization not working [1]. The attitude of affective commitment to the organization can be determined through three factors, namely, (1) belief in the values and goals of the organization, (2) willingness to work hard on behalf of the organization and efforts to maintain the good name of the organization, (3) the desire to remain a member of the organization [21].

In recent years, there has been a lot of literature related to affective commitment with various research subjects, research variables that affect an affective commitment and other research methods. However, there are no studies based on bibliometric analysis published in Scopus indexed journals. With so many articles related to commitment that have been researched by researchers and published, it is necessary to carry out other research that adopts a method that includes mapping all scientific literature to be able to evaluate the latest research developments and the contributions of researchers from various fields of science so as to allow the emergence of new research roadmaps. Bibliometric analysis can be used to see the distribution of the number of publications and citations from various scientific articles [15]. This analysis can reveal research subjects from most of the publications and research opportunities for affective commitment especially affective commitment among teachers.

Based on this, the authors are interested in conducting bibliometric research related to affective commitment to determine the development of research trends related to affective commitment among teachers. In addition, the results of this study can be relied upon to be a reference or guide for further researchers in conducting research related to affective commitment to teachers.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, a bibliometric analysis approach was used. Bibliometric techniques were first used by scientists in the information field to study the growth and distribution of published scientific articles [12]. Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative method for reflecting and describing published academic articles. Bibliometric mapping will help visualize publication metadata, which can be useful for the scientific community and the public so that it is easier to manage and process into more useful knowledge, such as visualization of keywords that can be used to identify a research topic in various disciplines, author mapping from certain scientific articles that can be used to identify the geographical scope of authors and scientific articles and to know the development of research trends related to the keywords used [11]. Bibliometric analysis is also called scientometrics which is part of a research evaluation methodology that allows to identify possible research directions and assists in determining the research subfocus using the author's keywords and title keywords [5].

The results of the study were evaluated based on the growth of the journal. In this study, bibliometric information was obtained from the Scopus Database. Scopus is one of the largest publication databases (data centers) which include scientific journals, books and seminar proceedings [6]. The search was conducted in February 2022 with 3 keywords, namely affective commitment, affective commitment in education, and teacher affective commitment. Keywords were used to scan articles related to affective commitment. The types of documents obtained from the Scopus database were only selected in the form of articles so that books, conference papers, book chapters, notes, conference reviews were not included in this research data. Based on the search results in the Scopus database, there are 4266 articles related to affective commitment, consisting of 297 articles on affective commitment in education and 83 articles related to affective

commitment among teachers. In addition, we get several results from Scopus, such as author, title, abstract, country/region, citation, author affiliation, and references related to the keywords used.

The bibliometric approach used in this study uses modern technology in the fields of information engineering, database management, and statistics, namely tableau and VOSviewer. VOSviewer is used to visualize and analyze research trends related to affective commitment from 1965 to 2021. While the use of Tableau is specifically recommended because it differs significantly from other visualization software by integrating data querying, exploration, and visualization into one process [16]. Thus, this research can be used to examine the development of research trends related to affective commitment. In addition, it can provide guidance, motivation and opportunities for future research [15].

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Research Growth and geographical distribution

Based on the Scopus database, the publication of affective commitment began in 1965 and increased significantly from year to year as shown in Figure 1. The highest number of publications related to affective commitment in 2020 was 504 articles. This increase in the number of publications indicates that there is an increasing interest in affective commitment research. In addition, the increase in the number of published articles from year to year shows the importance of affective commitment in education. Furthermore, on the Scopus database, the total number of countries that have contributed to publications related to affective commitment is obtained. The distribution of article publications from each country is determined based on the author's affiliation. There are 106 countries that contribute publications related to affective commitment, of which the top 10 publishing countries can be seen in Figure 2. Based on the figure, it can be seen that the largest number of articles was published by the United States with 1355 publications (31.76%), the second was Canada with 373 publications (8.74%), Australia and UK contributed 336 publications (7.87%) and 335 publications (7.85%), China, Germany and India each contributed 334 publications (7,825). , 194 publications (4.54%) and 191 publications (4.47%). Spain, Netherlands and South Korea with 181 publications (4.42.4%), 165 publications.

Fig. 1: The number of documents per year

Fig. 2: Geographical distribution

B. Source title

Based on scopus database that had been analyzed using VOSviewer, we obtained the top source title that affective commitment articles have been published. The result are shown

in table 1. From the table 1, we can see that International journal of human resource management has the most documents related to affective commitment, followed by personnel review, sustaibility (switzerland) and frontiers in psychology.

Source Title	Total Documents	Percentage
International journal of human resource management	38	0,89
Personnel review	32	0,75
Sustainability (switzerland)	31	0,73
Frontiers in psychology	28	0,66
Journal of managerial psychology	19	0,45
Journal of business ethics	17	0,40
Journal of vocational behavior	17	0,40
Intenational journal of organizational analysis	17	0,40
Journal of business research	16	0,38
International journal of hospitality management	15	0,35

Table 1: Top 10 Documents By Source Title

C. Most relevant Affiliation

Based on scopus database, we obtained the most relevant institutions that publish research related to affective commitment. Figure 3 shows that the top two intitutions are in Canada and London. They are HEC Montréal with 75 articles (1,76%) and The univeristy of Western Ontario with 52 articles (1,22%). The other top relevant intitutions from Australia

(Monash University), Hongkong (Hong Kong Polytechnic University), Australia (The University of Queensland), Hongkong (City University of Hong Kong), United States (Pennsylvania State University), Belgium (Universiteit Gent and Université Catholique de Louvain) and Portugal (Universidade de Lisboa).

Fig. 3: Most relevant affiliation

D. Most highly cited authors

Based on scopus database that had been analyzed using VOSviewer, we obtained the most cited authors in the area of affective commitment through their publications. Table 2 shows that Morin A.J.S is the most cited authors with 543 citations.

Rank	Author	Citation	Total Link Strength
1	Morin A.J.S	543	68
2	Meyer J.P.	410	57
3	Vandenberghe C.	259	30
4	Han H.	148	2
5	Buch R.	142	4
6	Naim M.F.	127	14
7	Islam T.	113	12
8	Neves P.	110	0
9	Lee S.	93	2
10	Lambert E.G	87	3

Table 2: Top 10 Highly Cited Authors

E. Most highly cited sources

Based on scopus database that had been analyzed using VOSviewer, we obtained the most cited sources related affective commitment. Table 3 shows the top 10 most cited source.

Source Title	Citation	Total Link Strength
International journal of human resource management	538	29
Journal of organizational behavior	508	28
International journal of hospitality management	496	7
Journal of business ethics	470	21
Journal of vocational behavior	438	31
Journal of business research	430	14
Journal of management	346	15
Personnel review	306	41
International journal of information management	284	4
Journal of applied psychology	216	12

Table 3: Top 10 Highly Cited Sources

F. The visualization of the topic area “affective commitment” using VOS viewer

In this study, the keyword “affective commitment” was analyzed using the co-occurrence VOSviewer. This analysis aims to analyze the content, patterns and tendencies of a collection of documents by measuring term strength and counting the number of keywords that appear simultaneously in the articles studied [11]. In the co-occurrence results using VOSviewer, each keyword is represented by a circle and each circle diameter and label size shows how often the keyword appears in the title and abstract. In this case, the circle size is positively correlated with the occurrence of keywords in the title and abstract [14]. All focus areas with the keyword affective commitment can be seen in Figure 4 as a visualization of the co-occurrence network by VOSviewer. Then, the distance between

one circle and another shows the relationship between keywords and the line in the picture represents the link between the two keywords [3]. Thus, the more often the two keywords appear together, the thicker the line between them and the shorter distance between the two circles indicates a stronger relationship between keywords [22].

Figure 4 shows the visualization of the Co-occurrence of affective commitment. In all publications related to affective commitment, there are 66 keywords at once. Figure 4 shows that affective commitment, leadership (ethical and servant leadership), productivity, social behavior and organizational support often occur together in articles published on the Scopus database.

Fig. 6: Network visualization of affective commitment in education

H. The visualization of the topic area “teacher’s affective commitment”

Figure 7 shows a network visualization with keywords or topics of affective commitment to teachers. From Figure 7, it can be seen that the publication of articles related to affective commitment among teachers is still rarely studied. However, affective commitment among teachers is an important aspect in determining the success of education reform and school

effectiveness because highly affective teachers are willing to contribute their extra efforts to achieve the school's vision and goals [20]. Thus, given the importance of affective commitment among teachers, the number of studies related to affective commitment and teachers should be increased. This can be a research opportunity for further researchers to involve articles related to affective commitment among teachers.

Fig. 7: Network visualization of teacher’s affective commitment

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examines all articles related to affective commitment, affective commitment in education and teacher affective commitment. This study uses a bibliometric analysis approach based on the Scopus database. This study succeeded in obtaining 4,266 articles related to affective commitment, 297 articles of affective commitment in education and 83 articles of affective commitment among teachers. All of this data was analyzed using VOSviewer software for data visualization, citation and metric analysis. The results show that the trend of affective commitment has started since 1965 and is increasing from year to year. In terms of number of publications, the United States is the country with the highest number of contributors publishing articles related to affective commitment. The most cited sources regarding affective commitment are the journal of human resource management and Morin A.J.S as the most cited author with 543 citations.

Based on this research, it can be seen that many studies related to affective commitment have been conducted. However, affective commitment to teachers is still rarely studied. For this reason, it can be an opportunity for further researchers to conduct research related to these trends. In addition, based on an analysis using VOSviewer, it can be seen that affective commitment, leadership (ethical and servant leadership), productivity, social behavior and organizational support often occur together in articles that have been published in the Scopus database and there are keywords that have the potential to be associated with affective commitments such as quality of work life, co-worker relations, turnover and employee welfare.

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